

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE AS DETERMINANTS OF INDIVIDUAL WORK PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 8

Pages: 1235-1250

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2908

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14636960

Manuscript Accepted: 12-20-2024

Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance as Determinants of Individual Work Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers

Loyd Kevin C. Martizano,* Erick T. Baloran
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study determined the significant influence of emotional intelligence and work-life balance on the individual work performance of public elementary school teachers using a quantitative research approach, specifically the descriptive-correlational design. A purposive quota sampling technique was used in selecting the public elementary school teachers as respondents for this study. Three adapted questionnaires, validated by experts and reliability tested, were used to gather the needed data for this study. Mean, Standard Deviation, Pearson *r*, and Multiple Regression Analysis were the statistical tools used. Results showed that their level of emotional intelligence was high. The level of their work-life balance was high. The individual work performance of public elementary school teachers was high. Also, public elementary school teachers' emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and individual work performance had positive and significant relationships. Moreover, Multiple Regression Analysis results revealed that emotional intelligence was the best predictor of individual work performance of public elementary school teachers. This means that every increase in emotional intelligence has a corresponding increase in the individual work performance of public elementary school teachers.

Keywords: *public elementary teachers, emotional intelligence, work-life balance, individual work performance, Philippines*

Introduction

Poor individual work performance among teachers is a universal issue that cannot be disregarded in Western and Eastern contexts. Poor performing teachers do not have good planning (Andriani et al., 2018), poor teaching programs (Irmayani et al., 2018), inadequately prepared for lessons, do not establish performance targets (Keoviphone & Wibowo, 2015), do not frequently attend class according to the scheduled time (Tao, 2013), lack enthusiasm in completing tasks, lack of teacher creativity in employing appropriate teaching-learning strategies and methods and who prioritize their personal duties instead of doing their duties as a teacher (Budiyo et al., 2020). These cause concerns for schools, including low student satisfaction with their schools, plans for student turnover, the expense of hiring new teachers, and interruptions in the delivery of instruction (Tehseen & Ul Hadi, 2015).

In the global context, Zepeda (2016) reported that of the 3.1 million teachers in the United States, five to 15 percent exhibit marginal teacher work performance as a result of ineffective instructional strategies, incongruous learning objectives, and content, challenges in meeting statewide content standards, ongoing classroom management issues, and inadequate preparation for instruction. In Sweden, teaching is one of the occupations with the highest rates of long-term sick leave due to various job demands, including administrative paperwork, frequent meetings that interrupt preparation time, and ongoing reforms and changes that necessitate reorganizing work and tasks. These had a negative impact on their work performance (Arvidsson et al., 2019). In addition, Uyanne et al. (2020) revealed that teachers' work performance in Ilorin West, Nigeria was low.

In Asian countries, the same is true for India, where Singh and Sarkar (2015) and Hasan (2014) have identified insufficient teacher monitoring, a lack of professional recognition, discipline issues in the classroom, workload, large class sizes, role ambiguity, a lack of transportation, long-distance travel, an inadequate supply of instructional materials, and few possibilities for professional growth as some of the factors deterring teachers' performance. In Indonesia, the initial observations in Muara Sugihan and Makarti Jaya schools showed low teacher performance (Budiyo et al., 2020). In Cambodia, low teacher work performance has been caused by ineffective incentives, a disconnected evaluation system, and a lack of opportunities to learn and share best-practice lessons (Tandon & Fukao, 2015).

Moreover, the Philippines' poor results in recent international tests, such as Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2018, Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), and Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) in 2019, show that the country is still struggling with a learning crisis. While many reasons affect how poorly learners perform, teacher work performance plays the primary role in these dynamics (Generalao et al., 2022). Thus, the study of Ganga and Haramain (2019) among teachers in Northern Luzon, Philippines, mentioned that low-performing teachers frequently result in low-performing learners. This is highly concerning because low-performing teachers have historically been one of the main contributors to pupils' poor performance. Moreover, Villegas (2022) mentioned a September 2020 report from the Philippine Business for Education (PBE) that, regarding teaching quality, 40% are absent teachers, and 35 to 60% delay their classes. Thus, one of the most important ways for a nation to support the overall quality of education is by strengthening the work performance of its teaching force (Generalao et al., 2022).

Further, it has been established that emotional intelligence significantly influences individual work performance (Shooshtarian et al.,

2013). In present times, numerous studies and works of literature have underlined the significance of emotional intelligence (EI) as an element that affects how well teachers accomplish their work, claiming that educators with high levels of EI are possible to do so (Asrar-ul-Haq et al., 2017). Additionally, numerous researches showed a strong and statistically significant association between emotional intelligence and teacher performance (Valente et al., 2020), corroborating with the findings from other studies linking emotional intelligence with higher levels of teacher performance (Poulou, 2017; Valente et al., 2019). Moreover, the significance of emotional intelligence is highlighted by the research of Mohamad and Jais (2016) on Malaysian teachers' job performance and emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence's four areas: self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy, and socialization influence teachers' ability to execute their jobs.

Likewise, work-life balance also influences the individual work performance of teachers (Mangaleswaran, 2018). Moreover, work-life balance substantially affects teachers' work performance, according to a paper by Johari et al. (2018). Also, Abdirahman et al. (2020) supported the idea that work-life balance impacts work performance by showing that it significantly impacts teacher performance. However, the academic and professional responsibilities of teachers that have piled up were spilling over into personal life, and they are already having difficulty balancing work and other elements in their lives; thus, these mentioned difficulties are associated with failing, under-performing and a lack of competence or quality (Quintana et al., 2019; Soomro et al., 2018)

Moreover, the researcher has yet to encounter a study in Surigao del Sur that determines the influence of emotional intelligence and work-life balance on the individual work performance of public elementary school teachers. It is in this context that the researcher is interested to determine the influence of emotional intelligence and work-life balance in relation to individual work performance of public elementary teachers in a district in Surigao del Sur. Thus, this study will contribute knowledge on the influence of emotional intelligence and work-life balance on individual work performance, which is new, especially in the context of the educational system in Hinatuan. Through the study's findings, the administrators can develop plans for enhancing teachers' individual work performance.

In this study, the researcher aims to contribute to Psychology and Education by determining the influence of emotional intelligence and work-life balance in relation to individual work performance of public elementary teachers.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the significant influence of emotional intelligence and work-life balance on the individual work performance of public elementary school teachers in Hinatuan District, Surigao del Sur Division. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of emotional intelligence of the teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. empathy;
 - 1.2. self-motivation;
 - 1.3. self-awareness;
 - 1.4. self-control; and
 - 1.5. sociability?
2. What is the level of work-life balance of the teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. workplace support;
 - 2.2. work interference with personal life;
 - 2.3. personal life interference with work;
 - 2.4. satisfaction with work-life balance; and
 - 2.5. improved effectiveness at work?
3. What is the level of individual work performance of teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. task performance;
 - 3.2. contextual performance; and
 - 3.3. counterproductive work behavior?
4. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. emotional intelligence and individual work performance of teachers; and
 - 4.2. work-life balance and individual work performance of teachers?
5. Do emotional intelligence and work-life balance significantly influence the individual work performance of teachers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a quantitative method, specifically a descriptive correlational design. The main goal of quantitative research is to collect numerical data and generalize it to different populations (Babbie, 2010). According to Creswell (2014), a quantitative approach entails gathering, assessing, analyzing, and documenting the study's findings. In the same way, Coghlan and Brydon-Miller (2014) defined quantitative research as a methodical investigation of events by gathering measurable data and using statistical, mathematical, or computational methodologies.

Similarly, according to Cohen et al. (2007), quantitative research employs a predetermined design that predetermines the research question and a data collection and analysis procedure. This research approach systematically uses numbers and anything measurable to investigate events and their links. Some of the examples that are frequently used with the statistical association are surveys and observations.

Also, the researcher utilized descriptive-correlational design to understand the phenomena's features and aspects and explain the relationship between phenomena. The change in one is the cause of or brings about a change in the other. This method assessed the relationships between and among two or more variables. Further, descriptive research is designed to create an impression or view of individuals' behavior, feelings, and thoughts (Stangor & Walinga, 2014). Furthermore, correlational research is a method describing and predicting how variables are related without the attempt of the researcher to change them (Babbie, 2010).

In addition, Creswell (2014) noted that descriptive-correlational research is a quantitative, non-experimental approach where the researcher uses correlational statistics to assess and quantify the degree of correlations between different variables or groups of scores. He went on to say that correlational designs are quantitative research techniques that use correlational analysis, a statistical technique, to measure the strength of a relationship between two or more variables.

As such, using descriptive-correlational design was appropriate for this study to establish the relationship between emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and individual work performance. It also established the strength of the relationship between variables and determined the influence of emotional intelligence and work-life balance on the individual work performance of teachers. This is to determine whether emotional intelligence and work-life balance influence the individual work performance of teachers. Thus descriptive-correlational design was utilized to determine and measure the level of emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and individual work performance and to quantify if there is a relationship among emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and individual work performance of public elementary school teachers in Hinatuan District, Division of Surigao del Sur. By examining the degree of correlation, which is represented as a number, one can evaluate whether two variables are related or whether one can predict the other (Creswell, 2014).

Respondents

This study had 200 elementary teachers from the elementary schools under Hinatuan District as the respondents of this study, divided into three districts: North, South, and West. They were chosen by using purposive quota sampling. Respondents were selected for this type of sampling based on the researcher's choice of a few particular traits. These particular traits are used as a quota for choosing the sample's respondents. Using this sampling, researchers collect representative data from a group (Bhardwaj, 2019).

There were 200 elementary teachers as respondents of this study since the researcher's scope is in public elementary schools, and there were only a few elementary teachers per school in the Hinatuan District. Moreover, out of 37 public elementary schools, only three had a population of more than 20 teachers, all of which were central schools.

The succeeding inclusion and exclusion criteria for the respondents were reflected in the study. First, this study's respondents were working and permanent professional elementary teachers in public schools with teaching load with at least six months of teaching experience and are affiliated with the Department of Education. Second, the schools and the teachers belonging to Hinatuan District had the willingness to take part in the study. Third, this study excluded head teachers and principals, public teachers from secondary (junior high and senior high school), and those working in an educational institution belonging to other districts outside Hinatuan, as well as private elementary school teachers and teachers from higher education institutions.

Instrument

The researcher adapted three questionnaires for the purpose of collecting the data needed. The first tool is the emotional intelligence questionnaire developed by Andrade et al. (2014). Public elementary teachers' emotional intelligence was assessed using a Validation of Emotional Intelligence Measure (MIE). The 33-item questionnaire contains five indicators: empathy with 12 statements; self-motivation with ten statements; self-awareness with four statements; self-control with four statements; and sociability with three statements. This research instrument has an original overall Cronbach's alpha of 0.932.

Second, the Instrument to Measure Work-Life Balance was developed by Banu and Duraipandian (2014). The 46-item questionnaire was made up of five indicators: workplace support (WPS) with 11 items, work interference with personal life (WIPL) with 14 items, personal life interference with work (PLIW) with 12 items, satisfaction with work-life balance (SWLB) with six items, and improved effectiveness at work (IEW) with three items. These five indicators have an original Cronbach's alpha of 0.864, 0.926, 0.888, 0.906, and 0.888, respectively.

Lastly, the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire was developed by Koopmans et al. (2014). The 18-item questionnaire was made up of three indicators: task performance (TP) with five items, contextual performance (CP) with eight items, and counterproductive work behavior (CWB) with five items. These three indicators have an original Cronbach's alpha of 0.78, 0.85, and 0.79, respectively.

The original Cronbach's alpha of the three adapted survey questionnaires was given. However, to establish construct validity, the

experts validated these questionnaires. They were subjected to pilot testing by selected teachers who were not the respondents of the study in order to have a new computed Cronbach's alpha. This was done to establish the reliability of the adapted survey questionnaires using the Internal Consistency method. The computed reliability of the emotional intelligence instrument was 0.945, the work-life balance instrument was 0.965, and the individual work performance instrument was 0.920, using Cronbach's Alpha.

Procedure

This study followed specific processes in gathering the data needed. First, the researcher asked permission to conduct a study with the Graduate School Dean of the University of the Immaculate Conception (UIC). Then, the researcher submitted his manuscript and ethics review forms to the office of the UIC-Research Ethics Committee (UIC-REC) for the release of ethical clearance. As the ethical clearance was released, the experts validated the research questionnaires before administering them to the respondents. Then, the permission was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent, then to the district supervisors/in-charge of three district offices of DepEd Hinatuan District.

After receiving the necessary approvals, the researcher approached the respondents to seek their consent before the study was conducted, agreeing with the established protocol and rules. The goals and methods of the study were clarified to the respondents. When there was consensus among them, the researcher distributed the final form of survey questionnaires and helped them complete the research instrument. An informed consent form was given to the respondents personally to request their consent prior to data gathering, following the mandates of the Inter-Agency Task Force for the management of emerging infectious diseases (IATF) to address COVID-19 risks, such as wearing facemasks, sanitizing and observing physical distancing. Informed consent ensured all respondents fully understood the study's objectives and purpose. The researcher certified that all respondents who signed the consent to be the respondents would answer the questionnaire on emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and individual work performance for at most 30 minutes in each section. Then, the validated survey questionnaires were administered and retrieved the same day after the teacher respondents had answered the survey questions. Lastly, the data gathered was handled with the highest care and discretion. Also, descriptive statistical tools were employed for data analysis.

Data Analysis

The statistical tools that were used for data analysis were as follows:

Mean. In this study, it was used to determine the levels of emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and individual work performance of public elementary teachers.

Standard Deviation. This tool determined the variability or disparity of public elementary school teachers' emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and individual work performance.

Pearson product-moment correlation. In this study, Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance in the individual work performance of public elementary teachers.

Multiple Regression Analysis. In this study, it was used to determine whether emotional intelligence and work-life balance influence the individual work performance of public elementary teachers.

Ethical Considerations

This research underwent an ethics review process through the office of the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the University of the Immaculate Conception (UIC) before the conduct of the study happened. This was to certify that the study was done ethically.

Social Value. The results of this study will reveal valuable information that will guide public elementary school principals, school heads, administrators, and teachers to improve their individual work performance by addressing the issues about their emotional intelligence and work-life balance. With the results of the study, they will become aware of the need to devise ways to deal with their emotional issues intelligently and in ways that would enhance their work performance and, at the same time, keep the balance with personal responsibilities. The administration may also realize the need to initiate strategic planning for the teachers. Further, this study will allow teachers to the specific dimensions of emotional intelligence that they could focus on improving since the results of this study could be shared with the faculty and staff of the Department of Education, Hinatuan Southern College (HSC), and stakeholders through research conferences, PTA meetings, and other formal gatherings. Aside from that, the HSC Library and the Department of Education will be given a copy of this manuscript that future researchers could use as a reference for forthcoming research works.

Informed Consent. The researcher asked for consent from public elementary school teachers through an informed consent form. First, the researcher sent a letter to the school principals informing the purpose and prospective respondents of the study, together with the approval letter from the school's division superintendent to conduct the study. The respondents then received informed consent. Respondents were thoroughly informed about what will be required of them, how the data will be used, and the potential consequences. A written informed consent was presented to them to obtain the respondents' full approval and required to be signed. Whenever they had questions while participating in the research process, they were allowed to ask questions and decline if needed. Voluntary participation in the study was emphasized, and respondents may withdraw their consent at any time. In addition, the respondents can discontinue their participation without penalty.

Also, the researcher indicated his desire to perform the research with informed consent so that respondents would be fully mindful of the objective of the study. Lastly, the respondents were also enlightened that the study's findings will be kept private to guard and preserve the confidentiality, self-esteem, welfare, and autonomy of the respondents.

Vulnerability of Research Respondents. The researcher did not consider this study's respondents vulnerable because the teachers who chose to join the study were consenting professional adults with a high level of maturity. In addition, the respondents were also given the freedom to decide whether they wanted to join the study. The respondents were not forced or misled into providing an answer if they found the inquiries too personal. Given the right to withdraw from the study whenever they felt exposed or emotionally affected by its findings, the researcher respected the respondents' choices. They voluntarily and directly gave their written consent to be involved in the data collection process upon recruitment. The data collected in this research were used exclusively to gather findings about the research problems. Information that was collected in this study was not used for other purposes. Also, the teachers agreed on the nature of the study, and the researcher established rapport and confidence to make the respondents feel at ease, safe, and more secure.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The researcher guaranteed the respondent's welfare by ensuring all respondents were adequately cared for and free from harm. Their safety was assured by providing them with a code instead of their identities. The researcher guaranteed the respondents' safety during this study by assuring their physical environment was conducive and secured, given that the data gathering was done onsite via face-to-face administration of survey questionnaires. There were sufficient space, decent ventilation, and appropriate lighting in the study's location. Risks were minimized to the extent that the researcher guaranteed that respondents completed survey questionnaires in safe settings. Furthermore, the researcher abided with the Inter-Agency Task Force for the management of emerging infectious diseases (IATF) to address COVID-19 risks which included the following: wearing face masks, maintaining social distancing, and providing hand sanitizers/alcohol for the respondents and the researcher.

The findings will be disclosed to the pertinent institutions as a sense of responsibility and openness on the researcher's side. After the study, the results will be shared with the schools to inform them of the research findings. Moreover, the time given by the respondents in the study was reciprocated as they were given a token of appreciation as a sign of benevolence in helping the researcher conduct the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The researcher abided with Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, in which the responses and identity of the respondents were not disclosed to anybody, in consonance with their fundamental human right to privacy, confidentiality, and correspondence. By all means, the researcher protected their privacy by ensuring no exposed respondents' records. The researcher ensured that nothing was shared and that everything remained private. To safeguard the schools' identities, the schools' names were not included. In ensuring the privacy of the respondents, they were represented by codes so no one discovered their identity except for the researcher. Moreover, the information gathered was electronically saved, and any hard copy of the data collected was kept safely in an area that was not accessible to other people.

Justice. No other person or group was required to subsidize the expenses spent during the study process because this research was exclusively the researcher's responsibility. The succeeding inclusion and exclusion criteria for the respondents were reflected in the study. First, this study's respondents were working and permanent professional elementary teachers in public schools with teaching loads with at least six months of teaching experience affiliated with the Department of Education. Second, the schools and the teachers belonging to Hinatuan District had the willingness to take part in the study. Third, this study excluded head teachers and principals, public teachers from secondary (junior high and senior high school), and those who worked in an educational institution belonging to other districts outside Hinatuan, as well as private elementary school teachers and teachers from higher education institutions. The targeted respondents were assured that the investigation was done appropriately in every way. The researcher ensured that respondents understood their responsibility to answer survey questionnaires openly, truthfully, and honestly.

The researcher gave all respondents mementos of appreciation for their significant contribution to this study as remuneration for the time spent collecting data. Additionally, to respect the respondents' shared time, the researcher allowed them to read their responses and verify their validity.

Transparency. At all times, the researcher avoided fabrication and misrepresentation of someone else's work as his/her own. Any communication concerning the study was done with trustworthiness and transparency. To safeguard the respondents' welfare, the researcher correctly implemented the methods utilized in the study. All the needed papers that support data analysis were included.

Further, the researcher shared the study's nature and objective and the methods used. The respondents were assured they could access the study results whenever they wished. The results, particularly the information transparency, will be thoroughly addressed. Finally, the researcher outlined the scope of his engagement and how he remained impartial while analyzing the data and presenting the study's findings.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher had a bachelor's degree in Elementary Education and was taking up a Master of Arts in Elementary Education. The researcher was devoted, dedicated, reliable, and credible in conducting this study. However, the researcher knew he had not been exposed much to research, considering that he was a novice in this method. Thus, he read pertinent articles and studies on quantitative research design.

Moreover, he sought advice from his mentor and the panelists as experts in this method. More so, the researcher habitually referred to his research adviser and other experts in the field. The advice of the experts helped the researcher mentioned above to acquire the data vital for the study, give insightful results that will be helpful to the school community, and even contribute to the body of knowledge.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher was assured that the resources required for his investigation were sufficient and readily available. References for various literature and research that supported the association of the variables in this study were found in books, online journals, unpublished theses and dissertations, and sources accessible in the university's e-library. Library and internet resources were made available for additional readings and references to reinforce and expand the analysis and interpretation of the data acquired. It was possible to communicate effectively with the research adviser and the members of the examining committee during consultations and the oral defense, thanks to the availability of functional digital devices such as laptops and cell phones. The researcher also sought help and direction from these academic specialists who could provide feedback and recommendations to verify that the results were legitimate and accurate. In order to support the researcher in doing the study and disseminating findings, a group of experts was identified who could offer insightful comments and suggestions.

Community Involvement. The researcher notified the schools and their heads by writing a letter to the division superintendent, district supervisors, principals, academic coordinators, and teachers to seek permission. The length of duration, possible impact, and results of the research and respondents were specified in the signed consent. Additionally, the respondents were made aware that the study's findings may assist them and their supervisors in gaining knowledge and awareness that will aid in formulating policies and enhancing their emotional intelligence and work-life balance, which affect each person's ability to perform well at work. The University of the Immaculate Conception will also receive copies of this book-bound publication. The results of this study will also be made public and available for broader audiences, such as presentations at conferences and research forums, as a reference for other academics and organizations.

Results and Discussion

Level of Emotional Intelligence of Public Elementary School Teachers

Presented in Table 1 is the level of emotional intelligence of public elementary school teachers in the Hinatuan District. Emotional intelligence has five factors: empathy, self-motivation, self-awareness, self-control, and sociability. The overall mean of emotional intelligence of public elementary school teachers is 4.04, described as high. This means that the public elementary school teachers' emotional intelligence is often evident. In addition, the overall standard deviation is 0.42, which indicates that respondents have ratings that are practically almost the same, implying the same consistency in the responses.

Table 1. *Level of Emotional Intelligence of Public Elementary School Teachers*

<i>Indicators/Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.1 Empathy			
1. sensing the feelings of our friends, colleagues, and pupils	4.49	0.57	Very High
2. understanding what friend, co-teacher or pupil wants without uttering a word.	4.37	0.62	Very High
3. recognizing when our co-teacher or pupil is in trouble	4.34	0.66	Very High
4. identifying easily other people's feelings, especially on our co-teachers or pupils	4.30	0.66	Very High
5. identifying our co-teacher or pupil's intentions as soon he/she starts talking	4.17	0.68	High
6. identifying how someone feels when he/she is in trouble	4.23	0.69	Very High
7. knowing when a friend, co-teacher or pupil needs help	4.32	0.68	Very High
8. recognizing how our co-teacher or pupil feels through their gestures	4.28	0.69	Very High
9. recognizing a co-teacher or pupil's feeling by the way he/she talks	4.32	0.65	Very High
10. knowing when someone is in trouble even if they don't say anything	3.96	0.80	High
11. finding out easily what a friend is feeling	4.13	0.70	High
12. recognizing whether someone is okay or not by their tone of voice.	4.31	0.70	Very High
Category Mean	4.27	0.53	Very High
1.2 Self-Motivation			
1. executing our school and office works and projects optimistically.	4.37	0.60	Very High
2. using our feelings to act wisely	4.30	0.65	Very High
3. working with enthusiasm on a personal project	4.37	0.64	Very High
4. achieving the goals that we set out for our life	4.31	0.64	Very High
5. facing any obstacle to get what we want in life	4.29	0.67	Very High
6. insisting on achieving our goals when facing strong obstacles	4.13	0.72	High
7. focusing on the plans we set forth for our life	4.34	0.66	Very High
8. guiding my present actions in accordance with the plans we've made for our future	4.30	0.61	Very High
9. planning situation to achieve our goals	4.41	0.64	Very High
10. feeling enthusiastic about our life	4.39	0.72	Very High

	Category Mean	4.32	0.51	Very High
1.3 Self-Awareness				
1. identifying all of our feelings		4.35	0.70	Very High
2. worrying about how we feel		4.11	0.78	High
3. distinguishing our feelings very easily		4.27	0.69	Very High
4. recognizing our contradictory feelings		4.27	0.70	Very High
	Category Mean	4.25	0.61	Very High
1.4 Self-Control				
1. pausing and counting one to ten before responding to provocations		4.03	0.69	High
2. controlling our impulses in conflict situations, both at home and at work		4.12	0.69	High
3. trying to react carefully when we are provoked.		4.13	0.69	High
4. trying to think before responding to something we didn't like		4.23	0.67	Very High
Category Mean		4.13	0.59	High
1.5 Sociability				
1. not reacting immediately to aggression		3.25	0.80	Moderate
2. not having an answer to an insult on the tip of our tongue		3.15	0.86	Moderate
3. not making decisions according to our impulses		3.35	0.84	Moderate
	Category Mean	3.25	0.73	Moderate
	Overall Mean	4.04	0.42	High

The findings support the study of Fu et al. (2021), which noted that educators with high EI are better at controlling their emotions, reflect on, and keep an eye on their behavior in the classroom as they work to advance their professional skills, experiment with new teaching strategies, and gain more knowledge in their field.

The findings also support the study of Gill (2017), which revealed that a rise in emotional intelligence levels promotes efficiency and success at work. The results are also congruent with those of Extremera et al. (2019) on Spanish teachers, who found that educators with higher emotional intelligence scores demonstrate greater coping resilience and higher levels of work performance. It also corroborated with the findings of Yoke and Panatik (2015), wherein teachers with high emotional intelligence are more likely to prosper in their careers. Among the indicators of emotional intelligence, self-motivation got the highest category mean of 4.32, described as very high, which is always evident. The item means ranged from 4.13 to 4.41. The item, insisting on achieving our goals when facing strong obstacles, got a mean rating of 4.13, while the item, planning situation to achieve our goals, got a mean of 4.41.

These findings support the assertion made by Mohamad and Jais (2016) that self-motivation entails creating goals and staying motivated despite any obstacles that may arise. Self-motivation engages an individual in daily activity and commits to any specific cause. Accepting responsibility for one's triumphs and failings is one strategy built on self-motivation. The findings also support the study of Cabahug-Fugoso (2019), who noted that individuals who are predominantly driven by self-motivation reported that doing tasks connected to their occupations is a lot of joy. Likewise, the results are in consonance with those of Tentama and Pranungsari (2016), stating that the greater the self-motivation teachers have at work, the better they perform.

On the other hand, the indicator of emotional intelligence which got the lowest mean, albeit high is the sociability, with a category mean of 3.25, described as moderate, which means it is sometimes evident. The item means ranged from 3.15 to 3.35. Meanwhile, the item not having an answer to an insult on the tip of our tongue got the mean rating of 3.15, while not making decisions according to our impulses got the mean of 3.35.

The findings, however, contradict the study of Trigueros et al. (2019), who noted that having high levels of sociability is important for building and maintaining positive relationships, as it allows individuals to communicate effectively, understand the perspectives of others, and respond to the needs and feelings of others thoughtfully and appropriately. In addition, the findings are congruent with Ukaigwe and Jack (2020), which emphasized that for teachers to carry out their responsibilities in the classroom successfully and efficiently, they need to create and manage their interpersonal relationships well.

Level of Work-Life Balance of Public Elementary School Teachers

Presented in Table 2 is the level of work-life balance of public elementary school teachers in the Hinatuan District. Work-life balance has five factors: workplace support, work interference with personal life, personal life interference with work, satisfaction with work-life balance, and improved effectiveness at work. The overall work-life balance of public elementary school teachers is 3.82, described as high. This means that the public elementary school teachers' work-life balance is often manifested. In addition, the overall standard deviation is 0.42, which indicates that respondents have ratings that are practically almost the same, implying the same consistency in the responses.

The present findings substantiate the claims of Sirgy and Lee (2018) that to attain work-life balance; there must be high levels of involvement in both work and personal time, as well as no social role conflicts in either setting. For work-life balance to exist,

significant degrees of association in occupational roles are necessary. If a person's work-related aims are vital to them and are achieved, a high degree of involvement in work-life is predicted to have an affirmative effect on that person's mood. It is also parallel to the study of Matula (2022), who concluded that having high levels of work-life balance translates to increased teacher performance. Thus, successful work-life balance practices serve the needs of both individual teachers and their schools and hence, have a vital impact on teachers' individual work performance.

Table 2. *Level of Work-Life Balance of Public Elementary School Teachers*

<i>Indicators/Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
2.1 Work Place Support			
1. working in an environment that is supportive of our family and personal commitments	4.51	0.67	Very High
2. allowing us to work from home when required by our school organization and school head	4.23	0.78	Very High
3. having adequate technology support (laptops, internet access, etc.) to be able to work away from office	4.02	0.82	High
4. having a school head who believes in having healthy work-life balance practices	4.38	0.66	Very High
5. an encouraging school head allowing us to go on annual vacations/time off	3.96	0.78	High
6. having a school head who believes in having happy people at work	4.36	0.74	Very High
7. having a school head who is concerned about the welfare of those under him/her	4.38	0.71	Very High
8. using our privilege leave which is approved by our school head.	4.34	0.74	Very High
9. having significant support from our school head / supervisor in ensuring that we have a healthy work-life balance	4.31	0.70	Very High
10. an encouraging co-teachers to use work-life balance initiatives if necessary	4.29	0.64	Very High
11. not facing difficulties in our personal life due to cooperative nature of the co-teachers / co-workers	4.04	0.77	High
Category Mean	4.23	0.55	Very High
2.2 Work Interference with Personal Life			
1. requiring us to work after hours to complete our routine tasks and urgent reports to be submitted	4.13	0.81	High
2. being concerned on the number of hours we work	3.92	0.89	High
3. failing to fulfill our family responsibilities as we have to spend more time in our work	3.60	1.00	High
4. being preoccupied with school and office tasks even after we get home	3.62	0.96	High
5. coming home from work too late to look after family roles	3.37	0.87	Moderate
6. spending more time at work due to the presence of demanding stakeholders and students	3.31	0.95	Moderate
7. demanding work which makes our personal life stressful	3.29	0.95	Moderate
8. feeling sleep-starved due to the amount of work that we have to do in a day	3.19	0.98	Moderate
9. suffering from work-related stress, which manifests as physical ailments such as headaches, insomnia, depression, blood pressure, etc.	3.28	1.02	Moderate
10. defining success as power, position, and money	3.20	1.03	Moderate
11. being irritable at home due to work-related stress	3.27	0.99	Moderate
12. believing that sacrificing personal life is the way an individual can be promoted immediately in the organization	3.34	1.02	Moderate
13. spouse/partner feeling uncomfortable due to our preoccupation with the work	2.93	0.99	Moderate
14. compromising our social engagements often on account of work	3.15	0.92	Moderate
Category Mean	3.40	0.73	High
2.3 Personal Life Interference with Work			
1. being preoccupied with home-related thoughts during work hours	2.98	0.86	Moderate
2. being distracted by personal/family worries while at work	2.87	0.91	Moderate
3. spouse/partner not understanding our work demands which impact on our marital relationship / romantic relationship	3.39	1.07	Moderate
4. experiencing family/home-related stress making us irritable at work	2.75	0.93	Moderate
5. believing that home responsibilities hinder our performance at work	2.75	0.99	Moderate
6. postponing doing some of our school work due to demands on our time at home	2.83	0.94	Moderate
7. being tired physically to discharge our work responsibilities at home due to school work overload at home	3.08	0.94	Moderate
8. making compromises on the work front to keep our family happy	3.02	0.91	Moderate
9. finding it difficult to complete work on time due to our preoccupation with societal activities,	2.80	0.91	Moderate
10. exceeding the amount of leave, we are entitled to take in a year	2.64	0.93	Moderate
11. interfering needs and demands of our family members with our work-related activities	2.78	0.93	Moderate

12. not concentrating on our work due to the dependent care issues at home	2.64	0.91	Moderate
Category Mean	2.87	0.77	Moderate
2.4 Satisfaction with Work-Life Balance			
1. being satisfied with our ability to meet the needs of our job and our personal life	4.12	0.68	High
2. managing our home and work demands successfully	4.12	0.66	High
3. being happy and satisfied with the contributions we make toward our home and family	4.16	0.67	High
4. being satisfied with the opportunities we have to perform our job well and yet be able to perform home duties adequately	4.11	0.68	High
5. having the time to reach our personal and professional/career goals satisfactorily	4.08	0.67	High
6. being contented with the way we divide our time between work and personal life	4.04	0.76	High
Category Mean	4.10	0.60	High
2.5 Improved Effectiveness at Work			
1. believing that a balanced life gives us the ability to function effectively at work	4.51	0.62	Very High
2. believing that work-life balance contributes to improved staff motivation and commitment	4.50	0.63	Very High
3. having satisfaction with work-life balance helps in building good teams, creative people, and positive attitudes toward work and life	4.53	0.61	Very High
Category Mean	4.51	0.59	Very High
Overall Mean	3.82	0.42	High

Among the indicators of work-life balance, improved effectiveness at work got the highest category mean of 4.51, described as very high, which means it is always manifested. The item means ranged from 4.50 to 4.53. Meanwhile, the item, believing that work-life balance contributes to improved staff motivation and commitment, got the mean rating of 4.50, while having satisfaction with work-life balance helps in building good teams, creative people, and positive attitudes towards work and life got the mean of 4.53.

The results align with the study of Podolsky et al. (2019), where they mentioned that other factors might also influence teachers' efficacy. For the majority of teachers, effectiveness rises with experience. When teachers work in a supportive and connected atmosphere and gain valuable experience, their effectiveness increases more quickly. Likewise, the results parallel Shahid and Azhar (2013), who noted that finding stability in work and household life is needed in both aspects and increases satisfaction levels, improving an individual's performance and output. Additionally, the results are congruent with Qayyum (2012), stating that motivated workers are aware of achieving particular aims and objectives in specific methods and focus their energy on doing so.

On the other hand, personal life interference with work was the indicator that got the lowest category mean of 2.87, described as moderate, which means it is sometimes manifested. The item means ranged from 2.64 to 3.39. Meanwhile, exceeding the amount of leave we are entitled to take in a year and not concentrating on our work due to the dependent care issues at home both got the mean rating of 2.64, while the spouse/partner not understanding our work demands which impacts on our marital relationship / romantic relationship got the mean of 3.39.

The results are congruent with the study of Sanz-Vergel et al. (2015), which revealed that everyday family- work conflict may result in daily interpersonal difficulties at work. The teacher becomes irritable due to trouble attending to work-related concerns due to family interference, reacting negatively to co-workers instead of utilizing more adaptive tactics like asking for social support or being positive. In other words, they become agitated quickly and start disputes with others. Likewise, the findings agree with Mohsin and Zahid (2012), who concluded that conflict between family and work might impact an employee's performance. Lastly, the results are also parallel to the study of Li et al. (2013), where they stated that home and workplace friction directly affects how well they perform.

Level of Individual Work Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers

Presented in Table 3 is the level of individual work performance of public elementary school teachers in the Hinatuan District. Individual work performance has three factors: task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior. The overall mean of individual work performance of public elementary school teachers is 3.94, described as high. Public elementary school teachers' individual work performance is often observed. In addition, the overall standard deviation is 0.39, which indicates that respondents have ratings that are practically almost the same, implying same consistency in the responses.

The results support the study of Kadtong et al. (2018), where they noted that teachers' work performance was evaluated very favorably and showed a high level of performance-related skills, abilities, initiative, and efficiency. However, the findings contradict the study of Nemenzo (2018) who revealed that teachers' performance in the Philippines could be more satisfactory.

Likewise, the results contradict those of Roberto and Madrigal (2018), who reported that the overall work performance of basic education teachers was deemed acceptable by teachers and principals. Their study suggested that more work must be done to achieve high or very high individual work performance.

Table 3. *Level of the Individual Work Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers*

<i>Indicators/Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
3.1 Task Performance			
1. managing to plan our school work so that it was done on time.	4.40	0.63	Very High
2. planning to the optimal level.	4.21	0.70	Very High
3. keeping in mind the results that we have to achieve in our work, especially in teaching.	4.34	0.66	Very High
4. separating main issues from side issues at work.	4.22	0.68	Very High
5. performing our school tasks/work well with minimal time and effort.	4.08	0.64	High
Category Mean	4.25	0.57	Very High
3.2 Contextual Performance			
1. taking extra responsibilities at school, such as being a coordinator and other teacher-related duties.	4.30	0.64	Very High
2. only starting new school tasks ourselves when our old ones were finished.	3.70	0.83	High
3. taking challenging work tasks when available.	3.97	0.72	High
4. working to keep our professional and pedagogical knowledge up-to-date.	4.18	0.61	High
5. working to keep our technical and professional skills up-to-date.	4.19	0.64	High
6. coming up with creative strategies/solutions to solve new problems, which can be used teaching-learning process.	4.23	0.66	Very High
7. looking always for new challenges in our job.	4.14	0.74	High
8. participating actively in faculty and parent-teacher association meetings.	4.53	0.63	Very High
Category Mean	4.15	0.53	High
3.3 Counterproductive Work Behavior			
1. complaining about unimportant matters at school and our work.	2.88	0.96	Moderate
2. making problems greater than they were at work.	2.51	0.83	Low
3. focusing on the negative aspects of a work situation instead of on the positive aspects.	2.38	0.86	Low
4. speaking with our colleagues about the negative aspects of our school and work.	2.70	0.93	Moderate
5. speaking with people from outside the school /organization about the negative aspects of our school and work.	2.43	0.91	Low
Category Mean	2.57	0.78	Low
Overall Mean	3.94	0.39	High

Among the indicators of individual work performance, task performance got the highest category mean of 4.25, described as very high, which means it is always observed. The item means ranged from 4.08 to 4.40. Meanwhile, the item performing our school tasks/work well with minimal time and effort got the mean rating of 4.08, while managing to plan our school work so that it was done on time got the mean of 4.40.

The study's results corroborate the analysis of Ricaplaza and Quines (2022) as they found out that the task performance of public school teachers in a district in Davao del Sur, Philippines was high. Furthermore, the results agree with the study of Damianus et al. (2021) as they found out that, as a whole, the task performance of teachers was agree/high. Furthermore, the results confirm the study of Gao et al. (2021), who found out that people who are high task performers frequently exhibit a high level of conscientiousness as well. In other words, they have more self-control, are more accountable, and are more persistent. They can concentrate better on their tasks as a result.

On the other hand, the indicator of individual work performance which got the lowest mean is counterproductive work behavior with a category mean of 2.57, described as low, which means it is rarely observed. The item means ranged from 2.38 to 2.88. Meanwhile, the item focusing on the negative aspects of a work situation instead of on the positive aspects got the mean rating of 2.38, while complaining about unimportant matters at school and of our work got the highest mean of 2.88.

The results are similar to the study of Ching et al. (2016) among teachers in the selected academic institutions in Taiwan. They found out that counterproductive work behaviors are occurring from low to moderate in schools. The results are also in consonance with those of Cuyos (2023), which showed that respondents had low counterproductive work behavior, such as complaining about unimportant work matters, speaking negatively about their jobs to co-workers, and speaking negatively about their work to people outside the company.

Significance of the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance and Individual Work Performance

Table 4 shows the relationship between the independent variables, emotional intelligence, and work-life balance of public elementary school teachers toward individual work performance. The result shows that the relationship between emotional intelligence and individual work performance of public elementary school teachers is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance ($r=0.419$, $p<0.05$). This further implies that the individual work performance of teachers is affected by

emotional intelligence, such as empathy, self-motivation, self-awareness, self-control, and sociability. Moreover, the result of the study proved the theory that emotional intelligence has a significant relationship with individual work performance.

Thus, it confirms the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), specifically the perceived expectations of how teachers deal socially and emotionally with themselves and others. It is pressured to maintain and uphold these expectations of empathy, self-motivation, self-awareness, self-control, and sociability.

Table 4. *Significance of the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance and Individual Work Performance*

<i>Variables paired with the Individual Work Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Emotional Intelligence Work-Life Balance	0.419	0.000	Significant
	0.256	0.000	Significant

*Significant at 0.05

This finding is congruent with the study of Yoke and Panatik (2015), wherein they found out that all four components of emotional intelligence, like self-emotional evaluation, others' emotional evaluation, utilizing emotion, and management of emotions, are significantly related to individual work performance. That indicates that teachers with high EI levels have been shown to perform better overall. In addition, the results agree with the findings of Myint and Aung (2016), which showed that employees' emotional intelligence had an affirmative effect on work performance both inside and outside the teaching profession.

Moreover, the result supports the study of Valente et al. (2019), which revealed positive correlations between emotional intelligence and teacher effectiveness, further confirming this. As a result, teachers who successfully cultivate emotional intelligence and emotional skills daily find success and fulfillment in their professional careers and personal lives.

Additionally, Table 4 also shows that the relationship between work-life balance and individual work performance of public elementary school teachers is statistically significant, having a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance ($r=0.256, p<0.05$). This further implies that the individual work performance of teachers is associated with the work-life balance of teachers. Moreover, the result of the study proved the theory that work-life balance has a significant relationship with the individual work performance of the respondents. Thus, it validates Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior, precisely the perceived behavioral control, as how teachers manage their time and juggle their responsibilities in the workplace and personal life.

This finding is in consonance with the study of Soomro et al. (2018), as they found a positive relationship between work-life balance and individual work performance. The result is also congruent with Anitha (2014), who contended that there is a strong link between work-life balance and individual work performance. From that standpoint, they may improve their ability to perform their tasks once they can equilibrium work and other obligations. Furthermore, the findings of the research by Abdirahman et al. (2020) and Johari et al. (2018) provided credence to the idea that individual work performance is significantly impacted by work-life balance. Both research revealed a link between individual work performance and work-life balance.

Singular and Combined Influence of Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance of Public Elementary School Teachers towards Individual Work Performance

The result of the regression analysis is shown in Table 5. The data revealed that between the two independent variables, only emotional intelligence could significantly influence the individual work performance of teachers ($p<0.05$).

This means that emotional intelligence has a statistical association or relationship ($r=0.419$) and causal relationship ($\beta=0.410$) with the individual work performance of teachers, implying that an increased change in the level of teachers' emotional intelligence is directly causing an increased change in their level of individual work performance. A beta standardized coefficient value of 0.410 suggests that for every one-unit increase in teachers' emotional intelligence, their individual work performance also increases by 41%.

Hence, emotional intelligence is considered the best predictor of teachers' individual work performance in this study. This implies that their ability to understand and manage emotions, build positive relationships, demonstrate empathy, adapt to change, and engage in self-reflection contributes significantly to their work performance as teachers.

Table 5. *Singular and Combined Influence of Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance of Public Elementary School Teachers towards Individual Work Performance*

<i>Individual Predictors</i>	<i>Standard Coefficient Beta</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Emotional Intelligence	0.410	5.133	0.000	Significant
Work-Life Balance	0.016	0.203	0.840	Not Significant
<i>Holistic Model</i>				
Predictors Combined	R2	F	p-value	Remarks
	0.176	21.022	0.000	Significant

*Significant at 0.05

The results align with the study of Gong et al. (2019), where they found that emotional intelligence plays a significant role in predicting work performance. In other words, the higher the level of emotional intelligence, the better their work performance. Moreover, the findings corroborate with O'Boyle et al. (2011), whose results underlined the significance of emotional intelligence (EI) as a predictor for work performance, generally contending that teachers with greater levels of EI are likely to perform better.

Furthermore, it can be noted that work-life balance only has a statistical association or relationship ($r=0.256$) with the individual work performance of teachers but shows no causal effect ($\beta=0.016$) on the individual work performance of teachers since the p-value is equivalent to 0.840 (> 0.05). This indicates that the work-life balance is somehow correlated with the individual work performance of teachers but does not necessarily show that work-life balance causes the individual work performance of teachers but does not necessarily show that work-life balance causes the individual work performance of teachers to improve. This goes to show that correlation does not imply causation. Hence, in its singular capacity, work-life balance cannot predict teachers' individual work performance without emotional intelligence. This means that work-life balance alone cannot fully predict the individual work performance of teachers due to the complexity of the teaching profession, role-specific demands, individual variations, external factors, and the influence of other factors on individual work performance.

This result is in contrast with the findings of Abdirahman et al. (2020), who noted that employee performance is impacted by work-life balance by showing that it significantly affects teacher performance. Also, the results negate the findings of Johari et al. (2018), wherein they reported that work-life balance significantly impacted teachers' work performance.

More evidently, the overall p-value (< 0.05) with an F value of 21.022, as shown in the holistic model, implies that the individual work performance of teachers is significantly predicted by combined independent variables (emotional intelligence and work-life balance). However, the R^2 value of 0.176 signifies that every one-unit increase of the combined independent variables (emotional intelligence and work-life balance) could lead to only a 17.60% improvement in the individual work performance of teachers. This accounts for a small effect size, for that matter. Thus, it infers that other factors equivalent to 82.40% could significantly influence the individual work performance of teachers not covered in this study.

With that, Kanya et al. (2021) stated that the other factors affecting teachers' individual work performance are teacher motivation, infrastructure, communication, cooperation, and others. In addition, Baluyos et al. (2019) stated that job satisfaction, school heads' supervision, and job security are the other factors that affect the individual work performance of teachers.

The findings of this study conform to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) of Ajzen (1991), who stated that a person's intention to partake in a behavior decides that one's outlook inclines the behavior's outcome, and intention to the behavior, the opinions of significant others in their lives about the behavior (subjective norms), and the conviction that the certain behavior is under the person's control (perceived behavioral control).

Conclusions

From the abovementioned findings, the following conclusions were drawn by the researcher:

(1) The level of emotional intelligence of the public elementary school teachers was described as high. This indicated that their emotional intelligence was oftentimes evident. Among the five indicators of emotional intelligence, self-motivation was the indicator that was always evident among them. This implies that teachers were resilient and were able to persevere through challenges. Their self-motivation gave them the determination and tenacity to overcome obstacles and setbacks since they viewed challenges as opportunities for growth and were willing to put in the effort required to achieve their goals.

(2) The level of work-life balance of public elementary school teachers in Hinatuan District was described as high. This means that work-life balance among this group of public elementary school teachers was oftentimes manifested. Moreover, public elementary school teachers' improved work effectiveness was often manifested. However, the results also showed that public elementary school teachers' personal life interference at work was sometimes manifested. It implies that teachers have achieved a certain level of professional success and productivity despite occasional challenges in managing their personal life within the work context. It is essential to find strategies and support systems to minimize the impact of personal life interference on both professional performance and personal well-being.

(3) Public elementary school teachers' overall level of individual work performance in the Hinatuan District was high. This means that teachers' individual work performance was oftentimes observed. In other words, this implies that their individual work performance is beyond average. Moreover, public elementary school teachers excelled in conducting their task performance which is always observed. Moreover, they scored low in their counterproductive work behavior, indicating that they only observed it sometimes. It implies that teachers generally fulfill their work responsibilities and meet the expected performance levels. However, it also means that there are instances when they engage in behaviors that are detrimental to the organization or their colleagues.

(4) There is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and the individual work performance of public elementary school teachers in the Hinatuan District. Emotional intelligence showed a positive significant association with individual work performance. This means that the more emotional intelligence the teacher has, the better their individual work performance will be. Furthermore,

public elementary school teachers' work-life balance and individual work performance also had a positive and significant correlation. This implies that teachers with higher levels of emotional intelligence tend to exhibit better performance in their work. Moreover, it means that teachers who have a better balance between their professional and personal lives tend to show higher levels of work performance.

(5) The data revealed that the individual work performance of public elementary school teachers was significantly influenced by the combined independent variables, emotional intelligence, and work-life balance. However, in the context of this study, emotional intelligence was the best predictor of the individual work performance of public elementary school teachers in the Hinatuan District. Thus, other combined factors could significantly influence teachers' individual work performance that is not covered in this study. This implies that public elementary school teachers actively and effectively utilize their emotional intelligence to increase their individual work performance. It also means that more than work-life balance is needed to fully predict the individual work performance of teachers due to the complexity of the teaching profession, role-specific demands, individual variations, external factors, and the influence of other factors on individual work performance.

Thus, the researcher suggests the following based on the findings and conclusions reached:

(1) Generally, the public elementary school teachers' emotional intelligence in Hinatuan District was high. However, it can still be raised to a higher level by conducting seminars and workshops among teachers, such as Teacher Professional Development Workshops to be done by external trainers or resource persons with expertise in emotional intelligence or by internal staff members with relevant knowledge and experience. They can also have classroom observations and feedback wherein school leaders or master teachers can conduct classroom observations and provide feedback to teachers regarding their emotional intelligence skills.

(2) Overall, the work-life balance of public elementary school teachers in the Hinatuan District was high. However, the results also show that public elementary school teachers' personal life interference at work is sometimes manifested, particularly when teachers claim that their spouse/partner does not understand their work demands which impacts their marital relationship/romantic relationship. Thus, school administration can conduct communication and relationship- building workshops centered on effective communication and relationship building for teachers and their spouses or partners. Also, trained counselors can provide counseling sessions among teachers. Moreover, school administrators can also conduct family days, parent-teacher conferences, or spouse/partner orientation programs can help them gain insights into the teaching profession, appreciate work demands, and promote stronger support networks.

(3) Overall, the level of individual work performance of public elementary school teachers in the Hinatuan District was high. However, teachers sometimes observe counterproductive work behavior. School administrators can also consider conflict resolution and mediation to address interpersonal conflicts that may lead to counterproductive work behaviors. Moreover, school administrators and teachers should foster a positive school culture and climate to thrive and minimize factors contributing to counterproductive behaviors. School administrators can also develop performance improvement plans for teachers displaying persistent counterproductive work behaviors.

(4) Considering that emotional intelligence and work-life balance have a positive and significant relationship with individual work performance, the researcher recommends that teachers maintain it since the better their emotional and work-life balance, they will also have a better individual work performance. School administrators can conduct emotional intelligence training to enhance their teachers' self- awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and effective communication. The school administrators and teachers can also consider reflection and self-assessment. Implementing these programs and strategies can help teachers maintain their emotional intelligence, promote work-life balance and improve their individual work performance.

(5) Since emotional intelligence is the best predictor of individual work performance of public elementary school teachers in Hinatuan District, it is recommended that school administrators integrate emotional intelligence in the curriculum, wherein teachers foster the utilization of their emotional intelligence for their benefit and for others as well. School administrators can also incorporate emotional intelligence into teacher evaluation as this will encourage teachers to prioritize and develop their emotional intelligence skills. Establishing peer coaching and mentoring programs where experienced teachers mentor their colleagues in developing emotional intelligence can also be implemented. Moreover, it is recommended that future researchers explore other variables not mentioned in this study that would also help improve the individual work performance of the teachers within and beyond school.

References

- Abdirahman, H. I. H., Najeemdeen, I. S., Abidemi, B. T., & Ahmad, R. (2020). The Relationship between Job Satisfaction, Work-Life Balance and Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance. *ADVANCES IN BUSINESS RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL*, 4(1), 42. <https://doi.org/10.24191/abrij.v4i1.10081>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision*, 33(1), 52–68. <https://doi.org/10.47985/dcidj.475>
- Andrade, A., Martins, R., Duarte, J., & Madureira, A. (2014). Atención Primaria Validation of Emotional Intelligence Measure (MIE) for the Portuguese population. *Atención Primaria*, 46, 92–100. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0212-6567\(14\)70073-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0212-6567(14)70073-3)

- Andriani, S., Kesumawati, N., & Kristiawan, M. (2018). The influence of the transformational leadership and work motivation on teachers performance. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 7(7), 19–29.
- Anitha, J. (2014). Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 63(3), 308–323. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-01-2013-0008>
- Arvidsson, I., Leo, U., Larsson, A., Håkansson, C., Persson, R., & Björk, J. (2019). Burnout among school teachers: Quantitative and qualitative results from a follow-up study in southern Sweden. *BMC Public Health*, 19(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-6972-1>
- Asrar-ul-Haq, M., Anwar, S., & Hassan, M. (2017). Impact of emotional intelligence on teacher's performance in higher education institutions of Pakistan. *Future Business Journal*, 3(2), 87–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbj.2017.05.003>
- Babbie, E. (2010). *The Practice of Social Research*. In Wadsworth Cengage Learning, USA.
- Baluyos, G. R., Rivera, H. L., & Baluyos, E. L. (2019). Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Work Performance. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 07(08), 206–221. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2019.78015>
- Banu, A. R., & Duraipandian, K. (2014). DEVELOPMENT OF AN INSTRUMENT TO MEASURE WORK LIFE BALANCE OF IT PROFESSIONALS IN CHENNAI. *International Journal of Management*, 5(11), 21–33. www.jifactor.com
- Bhardwaj, P. (2019). Types of sampling in research. *Journal of the Practice of Cardiovascular Sciences*, 5(3), 157. https://doi.org/10.4103/jpcs.jpcs_62_19
- Budiyono, Lian, B., & Fitria, H. (2020). The Influence of Principal Supervision and Organizational Climate toward Teacher's Performance. *Covid-19: Challenge to SDG and Globalization*, 2(III), 103–115.
- Cabahug-Fugoso, G. Lou. (2019). A Philippine Setting: Work Motivation of Employees and Motivational Strategy Evaluation In an Industrial Establishment. *Abstract Proceedings International Scholars Conference*, 7(1), 1359–1372. <https://doi.org/10.35974/isc.v7i1.2093>
- Ching, G. S., Tsay, W.-R., Hu, Y.-L., & Hung, C.-H. (2016). Counterproductive work behaviors within academic institutions: A myth or a reality. *International Journal of Research Studies in Psychology*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrsp.2016.1629>
- Coghlan, D., & Brydon-Miller, M. (2014). *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Action Research*. In SAGE Publications, Inc, United Kingdom. <https://www.ptonline.com/articles/how-to-get-better-mfi-results%0Aamuhammadkahfi16060474066@mhs.unesa.ac.id>
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2007). *Research Methods in Education* (6th Edition). In Routledge, New York USA. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315158501-17>
- Creswell, J. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches* (3rd Ed.). SAGE Publications, Inc, California. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nq/s4-I.25.577-c>
- Damianus, A., Luciano, A., Ubasa, A., & Magallanes, T. (2021). Attitude Management To cite this version : A new decade for social changes.
- Extremera, N., Mérida-López, S., Sánchez-Álvarez, N., Quintana-Orts, C., & Rey, L. (2019). A friend is a treasure: emotional intelligence, workplace social support and teacher engagement. *Praxis & Saber*, 10(24), 69–92. <https://doi.org/10.19053/22160159.v10.n25.2019.10003>
- Fu, W., Wang, C., Tang, W., Lu, S., & Wang, Y. (2021). Emotional Intelligence and Well-Being of Special Education Teachers in China: The Mediating Role of Work-Engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12(August), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.696561>
- Ganga, J., & Haramain, T. (2019). Undesirable Factors Affecting the Performance Level of Public Secondary School Teachers in Northern Luzon, Philippines. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 6(2), 219–230. https://www.ijrrjournal.com/IJRR_Vol.6_Issue.2_Feb2019/Abstract_IJRR0031.html
- Generalao, I. N., Ducanes, G., Yee, K. M., & David, C. (2022). Teacher Education in the Philippines: Are We Meeting the Demand for Quality? *Philippine Journal of Public Policy: Interdisciplinary Development Perspectives*, 2022, 1–65. <https://doi.org/10.54096/iene4805>
- Gill, S. G. (2017). An Exploration of Emotional Intelligence in Teaching: Comparison between Practitioners from the United Kingdom & India. *Journal of Psychology & Clinical Psychiatry*, 7(2), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.15406/jpcpy.2017.07.00430>
- Gong, Z., Chen, Y., & Wang, Y. (2019). The Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Job Burnout and Job Performance: Mediating Effect of Psychological Capital. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10(December), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02707>

- Hasan, A. (2014). A Study of Occupational Stress of Primary School Teachers. *Educationia Confab*, 3(4), 11–19.
- Irmayani, H., Wardiah, D., & Kristiawan., M. (2018). The strategy of SD Pusri in improving educational quality. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 7(7), 113–121.
- Johari, J., Yean Tan, F., & Tjik Zulkarnain, Z. I. (2018). Autonomy, workload, work-life balance and job performance among teachers. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 32(1), 107–120. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-10-2016-0226>
- Kadtong, M. L., Unos, M., Antok, T. D., & Midzid, M. A. E. (2018). Teaching Performance and Job Satisfaction Among Teachers at Region XII. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3169846>
- Kanya, N., Fathoni, A. B., & Ramdani, Z. (2021). Factors affecting teacher performance. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(4), 1462–1468. <https://doi.org/10.11591/IJERE.V10I4.21693>
- Keoviphone, C., & Wibowo, U. B. (2015). FACTORS DISCOURAGING STUDENTS FROM SCHOOLING: A CASE STUDY AT JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL IN LAOS. 1(1).
- Koopmans, L., Bernaards, C. M., Hildebrandt, V. H., De Vet, H. C. W., & Van Der Beek, A. J. (2014). Construct validity of the individual work performance questionnaire. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 56(3), 331–337. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0000000000000113>
- Li, C., Lu, J., & Zhang, Y. (2013). Cross-domain effects of work-family conflict on organizational commitment and performance. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 41(10), 1641–1654. <https://doi.org/10.2224/sbp.2013.41.10.1641>
- Mangaleswaran, T. (2018). Relationship between Work-Life Balance and Job Performance of Employees. 20(5), 11–16. <https://doi.org/10.9790/487X-2005011116>
- Mohamad, M., & Jais, J. (2016). Emotional Intelligence and Job Performance: A Study among Malaysian Teachers. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35(October 2015), 674–682. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(16\)00083-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(16)00083-6)
- Mohsin, M., & Zahid, H. (2012). The predictors and performance-related outcomes of bi-directional work-family conflict: An empirical study. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(46), 11504–11510. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ajbm11.1784>
- Myint, A. A., & Aung, A. A. (2016). The Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Job Performance of Myanmar School Teachers. 1(1).
- Nemenzo, N. (2018). Problems Encountered by Teachers in the Teaching-Learning Process: A Basis of an Action Plan. *Teachers Perceptions on Daily Writing Lesson Plans: Its Implications to Teacher Performance*, April 2018. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324606765_Problems_Encountered_by_Teachers_in_the_TeachingLearning_Process_A_Basis_of_an_Action_Plan
- O’boyle, E. H., Humphrey, R. H., Pollack, J. M., Hawver, T. H., & Story, P. A. (2011). The relation between emotional intelligence and job performance: A meta-analysis. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.714>
- Podolsky, A., Kini, T., & Darling-Hammond, L. (2019). Does teaching experience increase teacher effectiveness? A review of US research. *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*, 4(4), 286–308. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPC-12-2018-0032>
- Poulou, M. S. (2017). An examination of the relationship among teachers’ perceptions of social-emotional learning, teaching efficacy, teacher-student interactions, and students’ behavioral difficulties. *International Journal of School and Educational Psychology*, 5(2), 126–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683603.2016.1203851>
- Qayyum, A. (2012). An Empirical Analysis of Employee Motivation and the Role of Demographics: the Banking Industry of Pakistan. *Global Business & Management Research*, 4(1), 1–14. <http://login.ezproxy.lib.umn.edu/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&AuthType=ip,uid&db=buh&AN>
- Quintana, C. B., Mercado, F. M., & Balagtas, A. O. (2019). Perception of STEAM Teachers on the Influence of Work-Life Balance on Well-being and Teaching Performance. *The Normal Lights*, 13(1), 2719. <https://doi.org/10.56278/tnl.v13i1.1243>
- Ricaplaza, M. C. B., & Quines, L. A. (2022). The Mediating Effect of Work Ethics on the Relationship Between Authentic Leadership of School Heads and Task Performance of Public School Teachers. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*, 1(6), 13–29. <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajmri.v1i6.1006>
- Roberto, J., & Madrigal, D. (2018). Teacher Quality in the Light of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 1(1), 67–80. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v1i1.13>
- Sanz-Vergel, A. I., Rodríguez-Muñoz, A., & Nielsen, K. (2015). The thin line between work and home: The spillover and crossover of daily conflicts. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 88(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joop.12075>
- Shahid, A., & Azhar, S. M. (2013). Gaining Employee Commitment: Linking to Organizational Effectiveness.

Journal of Management Research, 5(1), 250. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jmr.v5i1.2319>

Shoostarian, Z., Ameli, F., & Amini Lari, M. (2013). The Effect of Labor ' s Emotional Intelligence on Their Job Satisfaction , Job Performance and Commitment Keywords : In 1997 , Mayer and Salovey described four abilities that contribute to emotional Intelligence : 1 . Perception : It involves accurate ver. Iranian Journal of Management Studies, 6(1), 27–43.

Singh, R., & Sarkar, S. (2015). Does teaching quality matter? Students learning outcome related to teaching quality in public and private primary schools in India. International Journal of Educational Development, 41, 153–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2015.02.009>

Sirgy, M. J., & Lee, D. J. (2018). Work-Life Balance: an Integrative Review. Applied Research in Quality of Life, 13(1), 229–254. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-017-9509-8>

Soomro, A. A., Breiteneker, R. J., & Shah, S. A. M. (2018). Soomro2018.Pdf. South Asian Journal of Business Studies, 8(2), 870–880. -work conflict with the employee performance-moderating role of job satisfaction%22, South Asian Journal of Business Studies,

Stangor, C., & Walinga, J. (2014). 3.2 Psychologists Use Descriptive, Correlational, and Experimental Research Designs to Understand Behaviour. BCcampus.

Tandon, P., & Fukao, T. (2015). Educating the Next Generation: Improving Teacher Quality in Cambodia. In Educating the Next Generation: Improving Teacher Quality in Cambodia. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-0417-5>

Tao, S. (2013). Why are teachers absent? Utilising the Capability Approach and Critical Realism to explain teacher performance in Tanzania. International Journal of Educational Development, 33(1), 2–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2012.01.003>

Tehseen, S., & Ul Hadi, N. (2015). Factors influencing teachers' performance and retention. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, 6(1), 233–244. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2015.v6n1p233>

Tentama, F., & Pranungsari, D. (2016). The Roles of Teachers' Work Motivation and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in the Organizational Commitment in Extraordinary Schools. International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE), 5(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v5i1.4520>

Trigueros, R., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., Cangas, A. J., Bermejo, R., Ferrandiz, C., & López-Liria, R. (2019). Influence of emotional intelligence, motivation and resilience on academic performance and the adoption of healthy lifestyle habits among adolescents. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 16(16). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16162810>

Ukaigwe, P. C., & Jack, I. F. (2020). Management of Teachers' Social Skills and Job Performance in Senior Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education, 7(4), 182–190. <https://doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0704019>

Uyane, E. O., Omoshalewa, L., & Balogun, A. O. (2020). Influence of motivation on teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West local government, Kwara State. Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn), 14(3), 345–351. <https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v14i3.16214>

Valente, S., Monteiro, A. P., & Lourenço, A. A. (2019). The relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence and classroom discipline management. Psychology in the Schools, 56(5), 741–750. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.22218>

Valente, S., Veiga-Branco, A., Rebelo, H., Lourenço, A. A., & Cristóvão, A. M. (2020). The relationship between emotional intelligence ability and teacher efficacy. Universal Journal of Educational Research, 8(3), 916–923. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080324>

Villegas, B. M. (2022, July 29). Addressing the Philippine education crisis. <https://www.bworldonline.com/opinion/2021/06/29/379015/addressing-the-philippine-education-crisis-2/>

Yoke, L. B., & Panatik, S. A. (2015). Emotional intelligence and job performance among school teachers. Asian Social Science, 11(13), 227–234. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v11n13p227>

Zepeda, S. J. (2016). Principals' perspectives: Professional learning and marginal teachers on formal plans of improvement. Research in Educational Administration and Leadership, 1(1), 25–59. <https://doi.org/10.30828/real/2016.1.2>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Loyd Kevin C. Martizano, MAEE
Hinatuan Southern College – Philippines

Erick T. Baloran, PhD
University of Mindanao – Philippines